

ACUTE OTITIS MEDIA AS THE MOST COMMON COMPLICATION OF RHINOSINUSITIS IN YOUNG CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Otitis media most often develops as a result of ARVI. In most cases, ARVI develops inflammation of the sinuses and congestion of the mucous membrane. Epidemiological statistics presented in the EPOS 2020 edition showed that the prevalence of ORSO is in the range of 35–45% in different countries of the world. Moreover, in children under 3 years of age, 20 cases per 100 children are registered annually, and in children aged 12–17 years – 25 cases. Acute otitis media (AOM) is one of the most common diseases in children and adults and one of the most common reasons for the prescription of antibiotic therapy, often unjustified. The review presents data on the incidence of AOM among children, as well as the most common viral and bacterial causative agents of the disease. The term “ototropic” was introduced in relation to viral pathogens that are more likely to cause the development of AOM.*

Keywords: *acute otitis media, diagnosis, treatment, young children and complications.*

Introduction. It has been shown that otoscopy does not provide clear information: hyperemia of the tympanic membrane may develop as a result of the child’s cry, but may be absent during an active process; purulent exudate may not accumulate in the tympanic cavity due to its evacuation through the wide auditory tube.

Purpose of the study: to study the features of the course of acute and recurrent purulent otitis media in young children.

The medical histories of 83 children hospitalized in the ENT department of the TashPMI clinic for acute and recurrent otitis media in young children in 2023-2024 were studied. Data were analyzed by age, gender and clinical picture. Of the 83 children hospitalized in the clinic with acute and recurrent otitis media in young children, there were 55 boys and 28 girls, i.e. the ratio of boys to girls is 2:1. The age group at the time of admission to the ENT department ranged from 1 to 3 years.

As a result of the study, catarrhal phenomena were observed in sick children: nasal congestion in 80 patients (96%), mucous discharge from the nose in 75 patients (90%), redness of the posterior pharyngeal wall in 25 patients (30%), cough in 54 patients (65%) and increased temperature in 62 (74%). Some children showed signs of intoxication: lethargy, loss of appetite, sweating and sleep disturbance. Temperature reaction was present in all children included in the study. Clinical signs of conjunctivitis were observed in 28% of children, with orbital complications in 2% and sinus thrombosis in 0.1%.

The assessment of pain depends on the child’s patience, and therefore a very careful comparison and real medical observation are necessary in order to draw an objective picture of the general condition based on the parents’ story and external impressions. The history obtained from the parents is very informative and the child screams when sucking at the breast, but behaves

calmly when spoon-fed. Indirectly indicates otitis media if the child screams in his sleep, reaches his hand to his ear, or rubs the back of his head on the pillow. Pressing on the tragus increases the child's anxiety.

Acute otitis in childhood is one of the most common inflammatory diseases, often accompanied by hearing impairment and, in some cases, progressing to a chronic form, which can lead to the development of hearing loss and other complications. Among all ear diseases in the general population, acute otitis media accounts for about 50%, and in childhood, this figure rises to 70%. Of all ear diseases, acute otitis media (AOM) constitutes around 30% of cases.

In Russia, there are 10 million cases of AOM recorded annually; 90% of children under the age of 3 experience AOM at least once, 7–8% suffer from it multiple times, and 65–95% have at least one episode within their first 7 years of life. Otitis is also a complication of rhinosinusitis in young children, alongside other complications like orbital issues and bronchopulmonary complications. In newborns, AOM is relatively rare (5%), but it tends to be significantly more severe.

The anatomical features of the middle ear in young children include the following:

1. The external auditory canal in infants is underdeveloped, short, and narrow, with the bony part represented only by the tympanic ring. Thus, in cases of acute otitis media, pressure on the auricle leads to a sharp increase in pain and child distress.

2. In children whose mastoid process is still undeveloped, the lower wall of the auditory canal is attached to the styloid process, lying almost horizontally and situated in close proximity to the descending part of the facial nerve, increasing the risk of facial nerve paresis and injury during antrotomy.

3. The tympanic membrane is round, located almost horizontally, and is relatively thicker than in adults.

As a result, when inflammatory exudate accumulates in the tympanic cavity, there may be no bulging of the tympanic membrane despite the progression of intoxication symptoms; pus can more easily penetrate the mastoid cavity through the wide entrance. Therefore, in questionable cases for infants and young children, indications for paracentesis are expanded:

- a) a sharp rise in temperature,
- b) significant pain syndrome,
- c) pronounced signs of toxicosis, especially neurotoxicosis,
- d) the appearance of symptoms of facial nerve paresis.

In weakened children, paracentesis should be performed as soon as possible.

1. The walls of the tympanic cavity in children under 1 year of age are thin, with areas of dehiscence, allowing for the unrestricted spread of infection.

2. By the time of birth, the middle ear cavities are filled with embryonic myxoid tissue, which serves as a good nutrient medium for microflora, contributing to frequent otitis in children.

The persistence of myxoid tissue can also lead to the development of bands and partitions that hinder the drainage of pus during middle ear inflammation, often resulting in hearing loss.

3. In early childhood, the pharyngeal orifice of the Eustachian tube is located at the level of the horizontal plane of the hard palate and the posterior end of the inferior nasal concha, with a posterior ridge surrounding the orifice like a semicircle. This should be considered during adenoidectomy, as it may result in scarring, stenosis of the Eustachian tube orifice, and subsequent hearing loss.

4. There are fissures between the parts of the petrous portion of the temporal bone that close by the 4th year of life. Consequently, acute otitis media in children can present severely with symptoms resembling meningism.

5. The pneumatization process of the mastoid process occurs simultaneously with the replacement of diploic bone tissue with compact bone, which mainly completes in ages 8-12 years, coinciding with the full development of the mastoid process's pneumatic system.

Among the complications is otogenic sepsis, which, due to the specificity of the pathogens (Enterobacteriaceae, atypical hemolytic streptococcal flora), is poorly responsive to commonly prescribed antibacterial drugs.

This is due to the following anatomical features: the tympanic membrane of a newborn is relatively thicker than that of adults, owing to the fibrous layer and the characteristics of the embryonic mucous membrane of the middle ear. The most common complication of acute otitis media is acute mastoiditis, while other serious complications include sinus thrombosis, otogenic meningitis, labyrinthitis, facial nerve paralysis, and brain abscess.

Methodology. In the early stages of acute otitis (eustachitis, catarrhal), the primary goal of therapy is to prevent complications. Conservative and surgical treatment methods are employed to restore Eustachian tube function. To recover ventilation and drainage functions of the Eustachian tube, vasoconstrictors or astringents in the form of drops are prescribed to reduce swelling of the mucous membrane and other agents. Children should be encouraged to blow their noses, and for infants, nasal contents are suctioned out with a special aspirator. For infants, vasoconstrictor drops are instilled 10 minutes before feeding to prevent pathological nasal contents from entering the Eustachian tube during feeding. Local treatment widely utilizes analgesic and anti-inflammatory medications, such as Otipax. After the inflammatory process subsides, otolaryngologists recommend procedures such as inflation and pneumatic massage. Therefore, both at the stage of eustachitis and at the stage of acute otitis media, systemic analgesics (ibuprofen, paracetamol) are prescribed for children. The Politzer method or catheterization is used for ear inflation.

Currently, there are no alternatives to antibiotic therapy (ABT) for the treatment of acute bacterial otitis media. ABT is undoubtedly prescribed to all children under 6 months of age, regardless of the severity of clinical manifestations, when AOM is suspected, even if there is no absolute certainty about the diagnosis. For children aged 6 months to 2 years, ABT is prescribed in cases of a confirmed diagnosis.

For children between 6 months and 2 years old, if there are doubts about the diagnosis, ABT is prescribed within 72 hours. Diagnosis of AOM is most successful in children over 2 years old, as their communication abilities allow them to clearly indicate the affected ear, and patients at this age actively participate in the treatment process. Only severe cases and the presence of otorrhea indicate a need for ABT. More than 60% of AOM cases in this age group can be treated without the use of ABT, especially in instances of otitis caused by *H. influenzae*. The decision regarding the appropriateness of antibiotic therapy should be based on the likelihood of complications from acute otitis and the possibility of the disease transitioning to a chronic form.

The mortality rate among patients with intracranial complications (brain abscess, meningoencephalitis, subdural abscess, etc.) reaches 18.6%. Adequate ABT can reduce the incidence of life-threatening intracranial complications from 2% to 0.04-0.15%. According to foreign authors, 90% of children with mild AOM recover without the need for antibacterial medications. This is particularly characteristic of AOM in children over 2 years old from favorable

backgrounds, when the disease is caused by viruses or *Haemophilus influenzae*. In children over 2 years, in the absence of pronounced symptoms of intoxication, pain syndrome, or body temperature exceeding 38°C for more than one day, only symptomatic therapy may be sufficient. If there is no positive clinical dynamics within 24 hours, immediate initiation of ABT is indicated.

Treatment of acute otitis media is defined by the stage of the condition, the predominance of specific symptoms, and the overall health of the patient. Considering the primary role of the tubogenic route in middle ear infection, active therapeutic measures should be focused on sanitizing the nasopharynx and nasal cavity. Swollen nasal mucosa hinders normal breathing and ventilation of the tympanic cavity through the Eustachian tube.

This complicates drainage from the tympanic cavity through the tube, especially since rhinitis is also accompanied by swelling of the nasopharyngeal mucosa, particularly at the orifice of the Eustachian tube. To alleviate these symptoms, the use of vasoconstrictors is recommended. In today's practice of otolaryngologists, there are numerous medications available for local treatment of acute otitis media. However, it should be noted that the local application of antibacterial drops is by no means an alternative to systemic antibacterial therapy.

Symptomatic therapy for acute purulent otitis should be combined with the use of antibiotics that are active in vitro against the pathogens of AOM. However, in 28% of cases of persistent otitis media, clinical symptoms of the disease remain. Russian researchers note the highest failure rates with the use of co-trimoxazole (75%) and amoxicillin (57%), followed by cefaclor (37%) and cefixime (23%). The most effective antibiotics are amoxicillin/clavulanate and azithromycin. Oral medications that meet all three conditions are amoxicillin and amoxicillin/clavulanate.

According to the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP), a 5-day course of amoxicillin in children over 2 years old with uncomplicated AOM has no advantages over the standard 10-day regimen. However, children under 2 years of age or with a perforated tympanic membrane should be prescribed ABT for 10 days. The use of high doses of amoxicillin (80-90 mg/kg per day) is justified in the presence of risk factors for resistant microorganisms. According to Russian recommendations, of all available oral penicillins and cephalosporins, including second and third generations, amoxicillin is the most active against penicillin-resistant pneumococci.

This is particularly relevant for children under three years of age. At the outpatient stage during the initial visit, the assessment of treatment dynamics should take place no later than one day. If it is not possible for an otolaryngologist to examine the child within this time frame, a decision must be made either for hospitalization or to ensure daily monitoring by a pediatrician.

Results and discussion. Based on the above, studying the features of the course of acute and recurrent purulent otitis media in early childhood is a pressing task that this scientific work aims to address. The objective of the study is to investigate the peculiarities of the clinical course and the incidence of otitis media in young children from a developmental perspective.

As a result of the research, catarrhal phenomena were observed in sick children: nasal congestion in 80 patients (96%), mucous nasal discharge in 75 patients (90%), redness of the posterior pharyngeal wall in 25 patients (30%), cough in 54 patients (65%), and fever in 62 patients (74%). Some children exhibited signs of intoxication: lethargy, poor appetite, sweating, and sleep disturbances. The temperature response was present in all children included in the study. Clinical signs of conjunctivitis were observed in 28% of children, with orbital complications in 2% and in 0.1% with sinus thrombosis.

The course of ear diseases in young children is characterized by clinical symptoms that allow a general practitioner to make an adequate diagnosis and determine the appropriate management for the sick child.

Furthermore, considering the potential for severe intracranial pathology as an otogenic complication, timely therapy for acute otitis media can save a child's life.

In the context of the widespread shortage of qualified pediatric otolaryngological care, a significant responsibility during the initial examination of a sick child falls on the pediatrician. The article discusses the modern classification of acute otitis media, the main morphofunctional prerequisites for the development of this disease in children, the characteristics of clinical manifestations, diagnosis, and the main treatment schemes for acute middle ear pathology in children. Thus, acute otitis media is characterized as an inflammatory disease of the mucous membrane of the air-filled cavities of the middle ear. This pathology is not an isolated disease affecting only the tympanic cavity, but rather represents a process that, to varying degrees, involves all cavities of the temporal bone. Based on the performed work, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Conclusions. The latent course and non-specificity of symptoms lead to untimely examination by an otolaryngologist, this especially often happens when the course is asymptomatic and there are no classic manifestations of acute otitis: hyperthermia, ear pain, suppuration. The latent course and nonspecificity of symptoms lead to the untimely examination by an otolaryngologist, which occurs particularly often in cases with few symptoms and the absence of classical manifestations of acute otitis: hyperthermia, ear pain, and purulent discharge.

The assessment of pain sensations depends on the child's tolerance, and therefore, it is necessary to carefully correlate and observe the patient to form an objective picture of the overall condition based on the parents' account and external impressions.

The medical history provided by the parents is highly informative; for example, if the child cries while breastfeeding but remains calm when fed with a spoon. Indirect indicators of otitis include the child crying in their sleep, reaching for their ear, or rubbing their head against the pillow. Pressing on the tragus increases the child's anxiety.

It has been shown that otoscopy does not provide clear information: the hyperemia of the tympanic membrane can develop due to the child's crying but can also be absent in an active process; purulent exudate may not accumulate in the tympanic cavity due to its evacuation through a wide Eustachian tube.

REFERENCES

1. Карабаев Х. Э., Маматова Ш. Р. Клинический случай орбитального осложнения при риносинуситах у детей раннего возраста //Евразийский вестник. – 2020. – Т. 3. – С. 78-82.
2. Маматова, Ш., Карабаев, Х., & Намаханов, А. (2023). Ультразвуковое исследование риносинуситов у детей раннего возраста. *Журнал биомедицины и практики*, 1(2), 63–69. <https://doi.org/10.26739/2181-9300-2021-2-10>
3. Маматова, Ш., Карабаев, Х., & Намаханов, А. (2023). Ультразвуковое исследование риносинуситов у детей раннего возраста. *Журнал биомедицины и практики*, 1(2), 63–69. <https://doi.org/10.26739/2181-9300-2021-2-10>

4. Маматова, Ш. Р., Х. Э. Карабаев, and К. А. Исматова. "АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ОСТРОГО РИНОСИНУСИТА ПРИ БРОНХОЛЕГОЧНОЙ ПАТОЛОГИИ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА." *Проблемы постковидной оториноларингологии*. 2022.
5. Маматова Шахноза Рамизидиновна, Карабаев Хуррам Эсанкулович, Агзамходжаева Нилюфар Шамсиддиновна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ОСТРОГО РИНОСИНУСИТА НА ФОНЕ БРОНХОЛЕГОЧНОЙ ПАТОЛОГИИ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА // *Re-health journal*. 2021. №2 (10). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osobennosti-diagnostiki-ostrogo-rinosinusita-na-fone-bronholegochnoy-patologii-u-detey-rannego-vozrasta> (дата обращения: 19.03.2025).
6. Маматова, Ш., Низамова, Е., Исматова, К., & Кахрамонова, И. (2023). Вопросы диагностики и лечения риносинуситов у больных детей раннего возраста . *Педиатрия*, 1(1), 151–154. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/pediatrics/article/view/26653>
7. Mamatova, S., Karabaev , X. ., & Asqarov , M. . (2024). ERTA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI RINOSINUSITNING ORBITAL ASOSLARI KLINIK VA DIAGNOSTIK XUSUSIYATLARINI O'RGANISH. *Development of Pedagogical Technologies in Modern Sciences*, 3(6), 201–204. Retrieved from <https://www.econferences.ru/index.php/dptms/article/view/15510>
8. Маматова Ш. Р., Карабаев Х. Э., Исматова К. А. АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ОСТРОГО РИНОСИНУСИТА ПРИ БРОНХОЛЕГОЧНОЙ ПАТОЛОГИИ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА // *Проблемы постковидной оториноларингологии*. – 2022. – С. 181-187.
9. Mamatova S. R. et al. DETERMINATION OF MICROORGANISMS MARKERS BY THE METHOD GC-MS AND EFFICACY EVALUATION of RHINOSINUSITIS // *Science and innovation in the education system*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 13-15.
10. Garashchenko T.I., Kozlov R.S. Acute otitis media in children. Prejudices of pharmacotherapy. *Pediatric otorhinolaryngology*. 2013; 3:31–6. [in Russian]
11. Karpova E.P., Belov V.A., Asmanov A.I. Validity of local anesthetic therapy in the treatment of acute otitis media in children. *RMJ. Mother and child*. 2023;6(4):411-416. DOI: 10.32364/2618-8430-2023-6-4-14 [in Russian]
12. Nussinovitch M, Yoeli R, Elishkevitz K, Varsano I. Acute mastoiditis in children: epidemiologic, clinical, microbiologic, and therapeutic aspects over past years. *Clinical Pediatrics*, 2004, 43(3): 261-7. doi 10.1177/000992280404300307.
13. Karpova E.I., Usenya L.I. Modern aspects of the treatment of acute otitis media in children. *Pediatric otorhinolaryngology*. 2014; 1:43–8/ [in Russian]
14. Zyryanova K.S., Dubinets I.D., Ershova I.D., Korkmazov M.Yu. Initial therapy for acute otitis media in children. *Doctor*. 2016; 1:43–5. [in Russian]
15. Karneeva O.V., Polyakov D.P. A modern approach to the treatment of diseases of the upper respiratory tract and middle ear as a measure for the prevention of hearing loss. *Pediatric pharmacology*. 2012; 9 (1): 30–4. [in Russian]
16. Siegel RM, Kicly M, Bien JP et al. Treatment of otitis media with obstruction and safety net antibiotic prescription. *Pediatrics* 2003; 112: 527–31. 13. Greenberg D, Hoffman S, Leibovitz

- E, Dagan R. Acute otitis media in children: association with day care centers – antibacterial resistance, treatment, and prevention. *Paediatr Drugs* 2008; 10 (2): 75–83.
17. Venekamp RP, Sanders S, Glasziou PP et al. Antibiotics for acute otitis media in children *Cochrane Acute Respiratory Infections Group* 2013. DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD000219.pub3 15. [in Russian]
18. Klein D. Therapy of acute otitis media in the era of changing sensitivity to antibacterial drugs. *MSRPA News*. 1999; 2:46./ [in Russian]
19. Smith NSP. Antibiotic treatment for acute otitis media. *Int J Pediatr Otol* 2013; 77. Is. 5: 873–4.
20. Karabaev, H. E., and Sh. R. Mamatova. "Clinical case of orbital complications in rhinosinusitis in young children." *Eurasian Bulletin* 3 (2020): 78-82.
21. Mamatova Sh.R., Karabaev Kh. E. "FEATURES OF DIAGNOSIS OF ACUTE RHINOSINUSITIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF BRONCHOPULMONARY PATHOLOGY IN EARLY CHILDREN" *Re-health journal*, no. 2 (10), 2021, pp. 84-89